

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Communication Pack

Delivering the Message
On Rural Regeneration

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1. Background information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title		Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
Project Acronym		RURITAGE	
Grant Agreement No.		776465	
Coordinator		University of Bologna (UNIBO)	
Project start date and duration		June 2018 – May 2022 (48 months)	
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	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)		

Table 2: Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Description
1	18/11/2018	Katrien Heirman	Structure of contents
2	22/11/2018 26/11/2018	Matthieu Guével	Filled sections 1,2,3,4,5,6, 7
3	14/12/2018	Katrien Heirman	Copy Edit
4	15/12/2018	Matthieu Guével	Filled additional visual materials
5	20/12/2018	Matthieu Guével	Final Revision

Table 3: Acronyms& Abbreviation

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage

2. Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of WP7 on Dissemination and Communication of RURITAGE outcomes and results.

This deliverable gives an overview of the activities and products related to the creation of the communication pack (logo, templates, brochure etc.), website and promotional kit for the project. These activities and products start from the ideas set out in the Communication and dissemination Plan (D7.1) and follow the communication strategy adopted by the consortium. The visual identity is aimed at ensuring a 'distinctive look and feel' across a diverse set of communication tools (e.g. promotional materials) in order to meet the information needs of the project target audiences. It is one of the most important communication and dissemination tools, which give the opportunity to reach a wider audience.

This deliverable includes background, rationale and information on the project visual identity and the use of the EU emblem.

The creation of the visual identity is based on the principle of simplicity and availability of the master identity in several versions. RURITAGE is one single project composed of many different layers and dimensions, including Rural Heritage Hubs (RHH), Replicators (R) and Role Models (RM) and 6 Systemic Innovation Areas (SIA). It was considered important to allow partners to focus on a specific SIA, and create a visual environment for that aspect, without losing reference to the general identity.

The creation of the website was built as a product of communication around the notion of readability and accessibility, designed to make the concept and outcomes of RURITAGE accessible to non-experts and the general public interested in rural regeneration and development. It was developed under DRUPAL 8, a technology that shall remain an international standard for the lifetime of the project, in terms of security and accessibility, notably.

For the purpose of communication and dissemination activities within the project, a series of document templates (press release, PowerPoint presentation, deliverable word report) have been developed and are available to the Project Consortium.

This report includes also an outlook of the communication tools and rules to be followed in order to achieve the goals set in the project in different communication and promotion activities performed by all the project Partners throughout the project duration. Communication guidelines have also been established to ensure that the integrity of the project identity is constantly maintained. This will allow greater efficiency in printing and other forms of reproduction.

Pictures of screenshots of all visual elements and materials presented below are for indication only. All master and final documents are available to all Consortium Partners at the following link:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1bZ3zPyn1Vf-32aIU-QNYk1_hE2tvpCNe

3. Visual Identity

One of the first actions in the communication activities was the development of RURITAGE project's identity. This identity is meant for non-verbal (often visual) representation of the RURITAGE brand, and it comprises important branding elements, including logo, printed materials and general brand style. It is worth mentioning that all current and future project related materials (and tools) are developed in English and formatted appropriately, in line with the H2020 visual guidelines.

A solid identity has been created for the consortium in order to portray a memorable, strong and easy-to use image for the project during consortium events, in the press, as well as to promote all actions and outcomes of the project through various communication channels, online and offline.

The Visual Identity for RURITAGE is based on several assumptions:

1. It builds on pre-existing elements prepared by the consortium during the preliminary phase of the project, including the set of colours and visual elements like the knowledge tree.
2. It sought to simplify these pre-existing visual elements to ensure they remain visible and recognizable even when displayed on reduced spaces or when in competition with other partners, names and logos, including on mobile phones, roll-up, posters and social media.
3. Modernizing the font and other materials: this project brings together quite a number of technical partners, and it was deemed important to add some lightness and movement in the RURITAGE landscape.

3.1 RURITAGE Logo

The main purpose of the logo is to capture the project's activities, as well as to be recognizable. The following logo was selected as the project logo.

The logo integrates the six SIAs with six different colours in the letter “I”, positioned at the centre of the word, (i.e at the heart of the project). It also includes the icon of the leaf after the project name. The slogan underneath the project acronym summarize the project ambition in four words.

1. The fair green colour was selected for the master leaf to present a sense of spring, rejuvenation, regeneration and fresh start. Other colours such as grey, yellow and brown were deemed not as appropriate in this regard. Considering the strong colour palette of the 6 SIAs, it was considered dangerous to introduce a new set of colours, with a risk to add complexity.
2. The icon of the leaf is more powerful than a mere set of coloured lines, and it is stronger and easier to use than the knowledge tree. The leaf conveys positive and intangible elements already present in the tree (spring, rejuvenation, organic life, rural background) and it conveys two other imaginary fields for the interest of the program:
 - i. The shape of the feather (bringing some additional lightness)
 - ii. The shape of the arrow, as an indication of movement and a direction towards the future, which is clearly in line with the objective of the RURITAGE project.

A comprehensive guideline for the use of the logo was provided to all partners.

The logo for the RURITAGE project was selected after careful review of several design options, including several proposals for the tagline/motto for the project. Preliminary options are presented below. A doodle was organized to vote on the preferred tagline. „Heritage for rural regeneration“ was chosen, and is an integral part of the logo.

Design options / proposals

3.2 RURITAGE Graphic elements

Other graphic elements were created for the consortium to be used in communication and dissemination materials. They are used when the repetition of the logo is difficult or not necessary, in order to build coherence and strengthen the visual environment of any presentation and allow for a greater flexibility in the communication process.

3.2.1 Systemic Innovation Areas Icons.

In addition to the coloured lines, 6 icons were created to present each of the different SIAs. The main purpose of this set of icons is to enable partners to present all different SIAs at once in a ‘bird’s eye view’, in a clear and powerful manner, in a limited space.

Pilgrimage	Local food	Art & Festival

Migration	Resilience	Landscape

3.2.2 Systemic Innovation Areas lines

In addition to the set of icons, SIAs are displayed in the form of the coloured lines landscape:

3.2.3 Systemic Innovation areas Banners

In addition, 6 different banners (one for each SIA) were reworked and reviewed from an initial graphic work. The main purpose of these is to enable partners to dive more in detail when presenting one specific SIA, without necessarily presenting all SIAs together. This can be useful in PowerPoint presentations or on Internet pages for instance. In this case, the master logo and the general overview of all SIAs should always be present in the introduction, before entering into each of the specific SIA.

The PowerPoint template presentation gives an example of suggested use. The above version should be preferred.

In some cases, to ensure better visibility or readability, and to avoid repetition, the use of SIA banners without the icon can be tolerated (see below).

3.2.4 Systemic Innovation Areas Logos

At the request of the partners, 12 additional logos were created, i.e. two logos for each of the 6 SIAs. This is to allow partners to present a specific SIA, should they need to do so. In this case, the master logo should always be present in the introduction of the presentation, before entering into the specific SIA. The PowerPoint template presentation gives an example of suggested use.

3.2.5 The RURITAGE leaf

As explained above, the leaf is the generic symbol of RURITAGE. Additional coloured leaves appear behind the main spring green leaf, to convey the notion of diversity and richness, and avoid presenting all 6 different SIAs, Role Models and Replicators at the same time.

3.2.6 The 6 SIA lines

The use of the coloured lines is another distinctive element of RURITAGE brand. Lines can be used vertically, as in the “I” letter at the centre of RURITAGE name, or on the vertical border of a page or document.

Verticality echoes to the concept of organic growth and quest for higher ground, as indicated in the knowledge tree. This notion of progress and growth is also conveyed through the “coloured corner pictogram”, to be used on cover pages.

3.2.7 The RURITAGE knowledge tree

The knowledge tree has been modified from its original version to convey a sense of roundness and richness: it now contains more leaves than the original version, making it richer. The branches are also thicker than previously.

The roots have been modified and complemented by dots, to convey the notion that knowledge flows both way, from top to bottom, but also from bottom to top, i.e. from Role Models to Replicators but also from Replicators to role Models.

4. RURITAGE templates

4.1 Deliverable Template

A template has been created to be used from now on for all RURITAGE project deliverables. The template is meant to present RURITAGE research, information and outcomes in a harmonized and accessible manner.

4.2 Press Release template

A template has been created to be used for all RURITAGE press releases.

4.3 PowerPoint presentation template

A PowerPoint presentation template has been created.

This template both includes a set of slides for general presentations about the RURITAGE project (indicated by the set of 6 coloured lines on the left-hand side). It also includes a set of slides dedicated to each of the 6 different SIAs, to enable specific presentation for each of these areas.

5. Printed Communication Materials

5.1 The Brochure

A visual identity alone is not enough to communicate the values and results of the project. Thus, additional materials were developed, in particular a brochure, a poster and a roll-up/kakemono. The brochure is meant to convey the key elements of the RURITAGE project, including the objective, the methodology and expected outcomes to current and potential partners of the project. The brochure will aid in the understanding of the project from a wide audience. The brochure has also been translated in French, German, Greek, Gaelic, Hungarian, Icelandic, Italian, Norwegian, Romanian, Slovenian, Spanish and Turkish.

The RURITAGE knowledge tree

13 rural areas which have proved and successfully pursued a heritage-led regeneration strategies have been selected as **Role Models**.

Role Models act as roots of the RURITAGE knowledge tree to mentor 6 **Replicators** in the development and implementation of their heritage-led regeneration strategies.

38 Partners, 18 Countries

More Info • Get inspired • Join us
www.ruritage.eu
@ruritage

Our Objective : to build a new heritage-led rural regeneration approach

RURITAGE seeks to transform rural areas in sustainable development laboratories through the enhancement of their cultural and natural heritage.

RURITAGE will gather stakeholders and local communities in a new form of collaboration, engaging them in a participatory and community based heritage management, ensuring ownership, capacity building and skills transference.

RURITAGE identifies 6 Systemic Innovation Areas as paradigms of heritage-led regeneration strategies:

- PILGRIMAGE**
- LOCAL FOOD**
- MIGRATION**
- ART & FESTIVAL**
- RESILIENCE**
- LANDSCAPE**

Participatory, community based approach, within 19 Rural Heritage Hubs

Rural Heritage Hubs will be the places to investigate and further boost the social innovation potential related with heritage in a participatory and co-creation process, promoting the capacity building and mutual learning approach from Role Models to Replicators and among Role Models themselves.

Key Outcomes : a set of tools for effective regeneration strategies

Within the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem, this 4-years project will make available multiple services and tools for rural communities to foster effective heritage-led regeneration strategies:

- RURITAGE Atlas**
An integrated and interactive web-based atlas mapping territories as the result of human-landscape interactions
- RURITAGE Replicator Tool Box & My Cult-Rural Toolkit**
A complete set of good practices and innovative solutions for rural regeneration
- RURITAGE Serious Games kit, DSS, Regeneration Guidelines**
A wide range of tools to foster change and collect feedback from rural communities
- RURITAGE Troubadour**
To foster people interaction with their rural landscape

5.2 The Poster

An A2 size poster has been created. The objective of the poster is to raise awareness and draw attention on some key elements of the project for presentation purposes. The poster has also been translated in French, German, Greek, Gaelic, Hungarian, Icelandic, Italian, Norwegian, Romanian, Slovenian, Spanish and Turkish.

RURITAGE
Heritage for Rural Regeneration

PILGRIMAGE
Heritage routes to sacred and historical places are drivers for sustainable and economic growth in many rural areas

LOCAL FOOD
Using food, wine and gastronomy is a widespread way to improve the economic and socio-cultural vitality of rural areas

ART & FESTIVAL
Festivals and arts attract tourists and bring economic resources to many rural areas, promoting youth entrepreneurship and a "creative rural economy"

MIGRATION
Beyond the challenges presented by the migration crisis, the arrival of "tourists" also creates opportunities for repopulation, growth and rural regeneration

RESILIENCE
Enhancing Cultural and Natural Heritage against climate change and disasters, rural communities protect themselves and boost economic growth

LANDSCAPE
Successful examples of participatory landscape management built on heritage is a crucial driver of rural resilience

19 Rural Heritage Hubs working together

38 Project Partners

13 Rural areas selected as Role Models

6 Rural areas Replicators for regeneration strategies

6 Systemic Innovation

RURITAGE seeks to transform rural areas in sustainable development laboratories, through the enhancement of their unique cultural and natural heritage potential.

June 2018 / May 2022

www.ruritage.eu
@ruritage

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 87130201

Working for Cultural & Natural Heritage as a way for migrants' integration (Germany)

Festival of lines - arts connecting heritage and tradition (Ireland)

A board for discovering local food products and traditions in Trøndelag (Norway)

Old traditions & modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmingsberg (Austria & Slovenia)

Social innovation & local traditions to react after a disaster in Marche region (Italy)

Integrated Management of Medra Gopalk in Gede-Balaraj District (Tajik)

World Heritage Landscapes (Columbia)

World Heritage Landscapes (Columbia): Apulia (Italy), WBK Atlantic Way (Belarus), Austrått Landscape (Norway), Vojvodina (Hungary), Maria Ut Way (Romania), Crete (Greece), Leivos Island (Greece), Asti Province (Italy), Carliño de Santiago (Spain), Douro Cultural Landscape (Spain), South Iceland, Haute Provence (France), Maria Ut Way (Romania)

5.3 The Roll Up

A roll-up version (1m x 2m) has been created. The objective of the roll-up is to raise awareness and draw attention to the project in a crowded environment, fairs, presentation on stage, etc. The roll-up has also been translated in French, German, Greek, Gaelic, Hungarian, Icelandic, Italian, Norwegian, Romanian, Slovenian, Spanish and Turkish.

RURITAGE
Heritage for Rural Regeneration

RURITAGE seeks to transform rural areas in sustainable development laboratories, through the enhancement of their unique cultural and natural heritage potential.

- PILGRIMAGE**: Heritage routes to sacred and historical places are drivers for sustainable and economic growth in many rural areas.
- LOCAL FOOD**: Using food, wine and gastronomy is a winning strategy to improve the economic and environmental sustainability of rural areas.
- ART & FESTIVAL**: Festivals and arts attract tourists and bring economic resources to many rural areas, promoting quality entrepreneurship and a "creative rural vision".
- MIGRATION**: Beyond the challenges generated by the migration crisis, the arrival of "tourists" also creates opportunities for regeneration, growth and rural regeneration.
- RESILIENCE**: Enhancing Cultural and Natural Heritage against climate change and disaster, rural communities protect themselves and boost economic growth.
- LANDSCAPE**: Successful examples of participating landscapes management built on heritage is a crucial driver of rural resilience.

19 Rural Heritage Hubs working together

38 Project Partners

13 rural areas selected as Role Models

6 rural areas Replicators for regeneration strategies

6 Systemic Innovation

Central of love – a site connecting heritage and tradition (Slovenia)

Working for Cultural & Natural Heritage as a way for migrant's integration (Germany)

Social innovation & local traditions to meet after a disaster in Marche region (Italy)

A brand for recovering local food products and traditions in England (Norway)

Integrated Management of Madra Geopark in Gule-Sabkha & Red sea (Turkey)

Old traditions & modern world along the pilgrim route to the monastery (Venice & Slovenia)

Replicators: South Iceland, Dozro Cultural Landscape (Spain), Carazo de Santiago (Spain), Haute Provence (France), Asti Province (Italy), World Heritage Landscapes (Colombia), Crete (Greece), Saronos Island (Greece), Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland), Austrikt Landscaps (Norway), Veszprém (Hungary), Maria Ut Way (Romania)

Partners: FAO, UNEP, UNESCO, etc.

June 2018 / May 2022 | www.ruritage.eu | @ruritage

6. Digital Communication

6.1 The website: www.ruritage.eu

For the purpose of the project, at the time when the project website was still under development, and in order to raise awareness and communicate basic elements about the project, UNESCO created, hosted and updated a temporary landing page on UNESCO's website (3 million visitors/month, within top 5000 of world's most visited websites). UNESCO digital networks (7 million followers) were used to promote calls for interest for additional role models, in addition to RURITAGE dedicated channels, while the latter were still under construction, and building up their audience.

The temporary landing page is accessible here <https://en.unesco.org/ruritage>

The purpose of RURITAGE permanent website is to gather all information and news about the project. All promotional materials should include a link to the website. It should be the portal where external stakeholders can get information on the RURITAGE project and to connect to the project management and administration. RURITAGE website is meant to be the showcase of all online communication material and also all the dissemination material (papers, conference abstracts, conference talk videos, posters). A web presence has now been established and will soon host all the communication material presented in this document. The project's team is committed to updating the website for the entire duration of the project's funding period.

RURITAGE website is accessible here: www.ruritage.eu

The website comprises project related information and is divided into several sections, bringing forward key elements of the Project, namely the 6 Systemic Innovation Areas as well as the 19 rural Heritage hubs selected so far.

The key principles for content production and graphic layout for the website are:

- **Simplicity and Clarity**, with a view to present a project that is relatively complex, with interconnected SIAs, Role Models, Repliators, Rural Heritage Hubs
- **Large photographs**, with a view to introduce the project with appealing and attractive visuals on rural areas, inviting visitors to learn more about RURITAGE
- **Dynamism and regular update** of news and events: the website should remain active, attractive

Based on these requirements, a first version of the website was built, taking also inspiration from other websites which were identified by the consortium as good practices (i.e. rock project, <https://rockproject.eu>, Robust <https://rural-urban.eu> and others), This version was discussed with the task leader and project coordinator, after which several improvements were made, especially regarding the main structure, the design (including a new set of icons), and the need to highlight Rural Heritage Hubs as a main entry point into RURITAGE's content.

The Website comprises a resource section, that will be updated regularly with additional materials and tools during the course of the project. Main tools and outcome of the project are presented in RURITAGE Brochure as well.

FOSTER HERITAGE AS A DRIVER FOR RURAL REGENERATION

RURITAGE establishes a new heritage-led rural regeneration paradigm able to transform rural areas in sustainable development demonstration laboratories...

19 Rural Heritage Hubs (RHs), established in each RM and 6, and 1 Digital Rural Heritage Hub (Digital RH) will involve local stakeholders in the formulation of the strategies...

6 SYSTEMIC INNOVATION AREAS

Based on past research and experiences, RURITAGE identifies 6 Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), which represent the Ruritage paradigm in which cultural and natural heritage acts as driver for regeneration...

Click on the images below to explore Ruritage 6 Systemic Innovation Areas and their related Rural Heritage Hubs:

EXPLORE ALL RURAL HERITAGE HUBS

RURITAGE involves 19 different case studies represented by 15 rural communities that will work together to build or to foster their heritage-led regeneration strategies...

RURITAGE aims at involving all members of society and motivate them to participate in civic, social, economic and political activities at local level...

Find here the full list of Rural Heritage Hubs.

LATEST NEWS & EVENTS

Three news cards with images and text: 'Migrations e accoglienza come elementi di sviluppo locale...', 'Writers reading afternoon for the public with special...', and 'Opportunities in the field of Action For Climate...'

NEWSLETTER

Newsletter sign-up form with the text 'Stay informed on Ruritage and its hubs activities. Subscribe to our newsletter.' and an email input field.

Footer section containing 'DATA PROTECTION' and 'LEGAL' information, including a disclaimer about the European project Ruritage and funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

With the Ruritage paradigm established in several rural areas, it is possible to identify a set of replicable models of regeneration able to boost heritage-led rural regeneration in other rural areas...

PILGRIMAGE

Heritage-led rural regeneration in rural areas through the promotion of pilgrimage routes to regenerate rural areas...

Three small images with captions: 'Cavities de Santiago (Dei Mezz)', 'Vic Maria Mariana (Vogel (Dach Mezz))', and 'Old traditions and modern music along the pilgrimage route to Montserrat (Piedra)'

LOCAL FOOD

Local food production and consumption in rural areas, where cultural heritage, food systems and rural communities...

Three small images with captions: 'Promoting and testing out for innovative food production in rural areas (Vito Mezz)', 'Cotton production in North Hubei Landscape (Hubei Mezz)', and 'In search for discovering local food products and traditions in Pagan (Pagan Mezz)'

ART & FESTIVAL

Heritage-led rural regeneration in rural areas through the promotion of art and festival activities...

Three small images with captions: 'Festival of Love Arts connecting heritage and traditions (Pagan Mezz)', 'Discovering contemporary art and culture in rural areas (Vito Mezz)', and 'Integrating the living village of the Middle Age (Dei Mezz)'

MIGRATION

The effects of migration on rural areas and the role of heritage in the process of rural regeneration...

Three small images with captions: 'Migration hospitality and integration in A&B Province (Dei Mezz)', 'Becoming migrants' integrator with nature in Lajos (Dei Mezz)', and 'Working for Culture and Natural Heritage to help for migrants' integration in Doo (Muzajani) (Borjassze) (Dei Mezz)'

RESILIENCE

Heritage-led rural regeneration in rural areas through the promotion of resilience strategies...

Three small images with captions: 'Learning culture for learning resilience in Crete (Dei Mezz)', 'Local innovation & local traditions to meet after a disaster in Marche region (Pagan Mezz)', and 'Natural Heritage as integrator: Culture and Natural Heritage for human resilience in South Hubei (Vito Mezz)'

LANDSCAPE

Heritage-led rural regeneration in rural areas through the promotion of landscape strategies...

Three small images with captions: 'A cultural area and heritage approach in Andalus (Dei Mezz)', 'Diverse cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Dei Mezz)', and 'W&A (S&A) way (Dei Mezz)'

Footer section containing 'DATA PROTECTION' and 'LEGAL' information, including a disclaimer about the European project Ruritage and funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

6.2 Social Media Channels

The RURITAGE project has three types of social media accounts: Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. All three of them are up and running. Overall, the consortium is urged to follow basic social media guidelines:

1. Use visual elements to make the tweets more visible (pictures/videos/Gifs/emojis)
2. Tag twitter accounts directly on the pictures you use to win space in your text.
3. Handles and hashtags to use: #Ruritage, #RuralHeritage, #Sustainable #GoodPractices

6.2.1 Facebook @ruritage

The project has a Facebook page to ensure wider dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. Facebook's target audience is the broadest of all social media channels used within RuRITAGE Communication Ecosystem and will help with disseminating the project to a wider audience. This calls for compelling and engaging content, to be further defined and in the course of the project. RURITAGE will also benefit from RURITAGE Partners' existing social media networks and communities to ensure wider dissemination, interaction, shares and likes. The aim is to amplify the message and get it to the target audience in the shortest amount of time.

6.2.2 Twitter @ruritage

One of the key features of Twitter is the information filtering by mentions of hashtags. Hashtags allow to quickly search and find information within the platform related to a certain topic. Basic hashtags relevant for the project will be (non-exhaustive list): #RURITAGE; #Ruralregeneration, as well as other hashtags associated with each respective SIAs.

6.2.3 Instagram @ruritage

As for Twitter, the use of information filtering by mentions of hashtags is crucial. Basic hashtags relevant for the project will be (non-exhaustive list): #RURITAGE; #Ruralregeneration, as well as other hashtags associated with each respective SIAs.

7. Obligations towards the European Commission

Unless the European Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- Display the EU emblem and
- Include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776848”*.

This project has received funding
from the European Union’s Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 776465.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purpose of their obligations under this Article, the partners may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means. Moreover, any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

END OF THE DOCUMENT